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Research Article

Effects of technological innovations on the economy growth in Nigeria

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Abstract

This paper explores the effects of technological innovations on economic growth in Nigeria, a country marked by a complex interplay of traditional practices and modern technological advancements. As Nigeria seeks to diversify its economy and reduce its dependence on oil, understanding the role of technology becomes crucial. The simple regression analysis will be used to do the ordinary least squares econometric analysis in this study to analyze and uncover the relationship between the topic variables, particularly information and communication technology, educational technology innovation, and banking technology innovation. Findings indicate that technological innovations positively and significantly contribute to Nigeria's economic growth. However, challenges such as inadequate infrastructure, limited access to funding, and a skill gap among the workforce hinder the full potential of these innovations. The paper concludes with policy recommendations to foster an environment conducive to technological growth, including investment in education and infrastructure, and promote public-private partnerships. Ultimately, this study underscores the critical need for Nigeria to harness technological innovations to stimulate sustainable economic growth and development.

Keywords: Technological, Innovation, economic, growth, Nigeria

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Background of the Study

Economic growth covers almost every discussion today because economic growth success allows a society to solve nearly all humanity's problems, such as poverty, unemployment, hunger, disease, dependency, debt burden, etc. Hence, it enhances employment, income, output, standard of living, health care, education, and self-reliance (Andreea, Olivera, and Florina 2015).

According to Eke, Agala, and Offum (2019), for economic growth to occur in any society, the available input resources must be utilized through a technological process to provide the quantity of output resources sufficient for consumption, saving, and investment. However, most societies do not have enough inputs to produce the output resources needed to stabilize the space for economic growth. Hence, the only viable approach for societies to become wealthier and maintain the space for economic growth is to keep getting more output from the same number of inputs, resources available, and technological innovation is the only device that guarantees such economic growth event (Eke, Agala, and Offum, 2019).

According to Eke, Agala, and Offum (2019). Joseph Schumpeter proposed technological innovation as the sure criterion for economic growth across nations. In the recent century, full attention has turned to technological innovation to achieve economic growth. As a result, for decades, economists have sought to improve their understanding of the effect of technological innovation on economic growth; the debate among researchers and policymakers revolves around how technological innovation accounts for the differences in economic growth across countries and over time. Schumpeter (1912) had argued that technological innovation prompts a new business to replace old ones. Subsequently, technological innovation was considered in the Solow growth model as a driver of the long-run output growth per worker. Indeed, it is a plausible argument that technological innovation is why more output can be produced today from a given quantity of capital and labor than a century ago (Romer, 1996, cited by Eke, Agala, and Offum, 2019).

Recently, these efforts have generated robust, substantive, and intellectually engaging findings to

benefit those interested in promoting economic growth by adopting and enhancing new methods. This has proven technological innovation as an essential driver of a positive economic growth performance, and the ability to undertake innovation has become a significant concern and a source of competitive advantage in economic growth (Nwosu, Ubi, and Fred 2022).

According to Mousume (2022), the growing role of technological innovation in economic growth has been lauded among European nations, as a survey for 12 European countries suggests that over 30% of manufacturing turnover is based on improved products and output continues to rise across the continent, while patent data shows a surge of technological innovation. A similar report is given in the United States of America. A recent analysis of the US economy found that more than 70% of the GDP in the US is the outcome of technological innovation. The US technology innovation is more global, arising from many sources and is spread more widely across sectors of the economy, thus broadening the basis for the US economic growth (Mousume, 2022).

Mousume (2022) posited that in the last decade, Asia has accounted for 52% of global growth in tech-company revenues, 43% of startup funding, and 51% of spending on research and growth. The region is experiencing a new wave of growth led by younger societies from India to the Philippines. Today's infrastructure investments are the platform for the next generation of digital innovation. In the last decade, Asia has expanded its infrastructure and technological capabilities, making economic progress and rapid strides in human growth, Human Capital, and innovation. Asia has embraced the digital revolution across retail, banks, education, information and communication, finance, transportation, e-commerce, healthcare, etc. (Mousume Roy, 2022).

Nigeria has had a noticeable technological innovation effort across industries over the years. The main features of technological innovations in Nigeria are the growing impact of information and communications technologies (ICT), Banking, and education (Nwosu, Ubi, and Fred 2022). According to Nwosu, Ubi, and Fred (2022), the financial sector has, over time, thrived with technological innovation, and products and services are available in the financial market. These

technological innovations include debit cards, credit cards, ATM cards, and mobile banking technologies such as point of sales (POS), Opay, internet banking, and other electronic payment products. All these efforts aim to bring about economic growth through technological innovation (Nwosu, Ubi, and Fred 2022).

The quest for technology innovation has become contentious across industries in Africa and Nigeria. According to Nwosu, Ubi, and Fred (2022), Today, more than ever before, innovation, enterprise, and intellectual assets drive the economic growth of a country. Technology innovation is instrumental in creating new jobs, providing higher incomes, offering investment opportunities, solving social problems, curing diseases, safeguarding the environment, protecting our security, and promoting transparency in organizations and governments (Štreimikien, 2014, cited by Nwosu, Ubi, and Fred, 2022). Speaking in agreement, Festus (2023) posited that in Africa and Nigeria, technological innovation has occurred in several sectors, including banking, ICT, and the education sector. According to the World Bank (2023), Nigeria's technology innovation index's average value is 23.28 points. This shows Nigeria's high performance in technology innovation compared with the world average of 32.09 points based on 128 countries (Festus, 2023).

Yet several stake holders in Nigeria has argued that the significance of technological innovation on economic growth is yet to be realized across various sectors and states in Nigeria, According to Darius (2015) opined that economic growth efforts has been deployed over the years in Nigeria yet; the level of economic growth has remained stunted. He posited that there is still a troubling economic growth situation in the country after several efforts of technology innovation inputs. According to Ozozoyin (2023), the government of Nigeria has sought diaspora involvement in rescuing Nigeria's economic growth, and a statistical report on Nigeria's economic growth variables has uncovered a poor growth performance. This report has become very glaring for the researcher to examine the effects of technological innovations on economic growth in Nigeria, to uncover if the various reported technology innovation efforts in Nigeria have affected the state of economic growth in Nigeria

Statement of Problem

Economic growth is crucial for addressing issues like poverty, unemployment, hunger, disease, dependency, and debt burden. Economists have been seeking alternative solutions for this problem throughout history. As a matter of concern, Schumpeter (1912), cited by Agala and Offum (2019), proposed technology innovation as a viable tool for solving economic growth problems by affirming that technology innovation is the basis for economic growth. Agala and Offum (2019) posited that technological innovation is the reason for the growth record in Europe, America, and Asia. It has become a plausible argument that technological innovation is the only reason for economic growth among nations and states today. Festus (2023) opined that Nigeria is experiencing several technological innovation efforts across various industries and states. According to Festus (2023), technological innovation has occurred in Nigeria in banking, education, ICT, and other sectors. In the financial sector, some technological innovation efforts are made through modern financial technologies such as debit cards, credit cards, ATM machines, point of sale POS, and mobile banking, with other products that facilitate using electronic means of payment. The World Bank (2023) reported Nigeria's average technology innovation index of 23.28 points, indicating high performance compared to the global average of 32.09 points. Despite efforts to improve technology innovation, economic growth remains stunted in Nigeria. Ozozoyin (2023) highlights Nigeria's poor economic growth, prompting the government to seek external intervention. The investigator investigates the impact of technology innovations, particularly in ICT, Education, and Banking, on Nigeria's GDP to answer this question.

Research Objectives

The general objective of this study is to examine the effect of technology innovation on economic growth in Nigeria.

The specific objectives are:

- To examine the effect of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) innovation on economic growth in Nigeria
- To examine the effect of banking technology innovation on economic growth in Nigeria.

- To examine the effect of education technology innovation on economic growth in Nigeria.

Research question

The following Questions will guide this research work

- How does Information and Communication Technology (ICT) innovation affect economic growth in Nigeria?
- How does banking technology innovation affect economic growth in Nigeria?
- How does education technology innovation affect economic growth in Nigeria?

Research hypothesis

- HO1: Information and Communication Technology (ICT) innovation does not significantly affect Nigeria's economic growth!
- HO2: Banking technology innovation has no significant effect on economic growth in Nigeria!
- HO3: Education technology innovation has no significant effect on economic growth in Nigeria!

Significance of the Study

This study explores the relationship between technological innovation and economic growth in Nigeria, using various theories to explain the relationship between variables. The empirical investigation provides data on the phenomenon and highlights its features. The report is relevant to policymakers, government bodies, banking firms, households, entrepreneurs, researchers, and students, as it adds to the knowledge on the impact of technology innovation on economic growth. It also serves as a reference material for further studies, recommending measures that positively impact economic growth. The findings will guide decision-makers in implementing technology innovation and promoting economic growth in Nigeria.

Literature Review

Anne August (2023) defines economic growth as transforming low-income national economies into modern industrial ones, often used interchangeably with economic development. It refers to the increase

in production of goods and services over time, typically measured in terms of GDP or GNP.

Munichiello and Charles (2023) define economic growth as the increase in the production of goods and services, influenced by factors like capital goods, labor force, technology, and human capital. Economic growth involves four phases: expansion, peak, contraction, and trough. It increases aggregate production, national income, and average marginal productivity, leading to higher incomes, increased consumption, and a higher standard of living (Munichiello & Charles, 2023).

Prabha (2021) explains that economic growth is influenced by physical, human, labor force, and technology, with increased working age population, tools, and labor-capital-raw material combinations leading to increased output. Real GDP, adjusted for inflation, is the most widely used measure of economic growth, encompassing all goods and services produced in an economy (Prabha, 2021).

Broadly, economic growth is taken to be the structural transformation of an economy by introducing more mechanized and updated technologies to increase labor productivity, employment, incomes, and the population's standard of living. Economic growth should be accompanied by improvements in infrastructure, as well as social, political, and institutional factors to facilitate transformation of the economy (Myint and Krueger 2016, cited by Prabha 2021). Economic growth is important for a country to reduce its poverty by providing more employment, higher incomes, improved goods and services, and the latest production technologies. However, the crux of the problem is that the framework for economic growth in modern technology, the industrial sector, and infrastructural facilities has not yet been established in many world countries for various historical and political reasons (Prabha, 2021).

Economic Growth in Nigeria

According to Darius (2015), over the years, growth efforts have been deployed, resulting in the 'foundational legacies that exist in Nigeria, because, compared to the abundant natural resources and other endowments in the country, the level of growth should

have surpassed this current stage. The socio-economic growth and growth of Nigeria is apparently stunted because of some challenges of inadequate infrastructure, insufficient finance, moribund bureaucracy, plethora of ethno-religious interests, deep-seated rancor between the political class and the civil servants, widespread nepotism and proliferation of mediocrity, and an entrenched political polarization. These major actors, together with other silent but salient issues, have held the state of economic growth in Nigeria hostage (Darius, 2015). According to Ozozoyin (2023), the government has sought diaspora involvement to rescue Nigeria's economic growth. Report of Nigeria According to the Nigeria Bureau of Statistics NBS (2023), Real GDP growth fell to 3.3% in 2022 from 3.6% in 2021, precipitated mainly by a decline in oil production. This led to a 5% shrinkage in the overall industry, which was offset by expansion in services (7%) and agriculture (2%). On the demand side, the decline in GDP growth was driven by contraction in public consumption (2.5%) and net exports (80%). Growth in income per capita declined to 0.8% from 1.2% in 2021. Ozozoyin (2023) posited that the fiscal deficit narrowed to 4.9% of GDP in 2022 from 5.2% in 2021 and was financed by borrowing, bringing public debt to \$103.1 billion (about 22% of GDP) from \$92.6 billion in 2021. Inflation peaked at a two-decade high of 18.8%, fueled by energy and food price increases and pass-through effects of exchange rate depreciation.

According to Joshua (2023), the Central Bank of Nigeria successively raised the policy rate, which peaked at 16.5% in November 2022 from 11.5% at the start of the year, to tame rising inflation. Buoyed by a relative improvement in oil exports, the current account recorded a small surplus of 0.1% of GDP in 2022, reversing three years of deficit. Gross international reserves declined 7.5% to \$37.1 billion (5.7 months of import cover). The nonperforming loans ratio stood at 4.2% in 2022, below the regulatory requirement of 5%. The capital adequacy ratio, at 13.8%, exceeded the regulatory benchmark of 10% in 2022. The multidimensional poverty rate (63%) and unemployment (33.3%) remained high (Joshua, 2023).

According to NBS (2023), Real GDP growth will remain subdued, averaging 3.3% in 2023–24, with

inflation elevated at 19.6% in 2023 before declining to 13.6% in 2024, reflecting efforts to shore up domestic food supply and the effects of contractionary monetary policy. The planned removal of the subsidy on Premium Motor Spirit (PMS) and increased revenue could further narrow the fiscal deficit to below 5% of GDP in 2023–24. The deficit will be financed by borrowing, biased toward concessional debt and longer maturities. Higher oil exports may not offset subdued capital inflows, with the current account projected to be in deficit, averaging 0.2% of GDP in 2023–24 (NBS 2023).

Technology Innovations in Nigeria

Information and Communication Technology ICT Innovation in Nigeria

Upgrad (2022) ICT innovation simplifies daily tasks and impacts economic growth across various sectors, including income, education, exports, exchange rates, employment, and standard of living, affecting various sectors of life. Upgrad (2022) has upheld the following as the effects of ICT innovations on economic growth

5G Network: The 5G network revolutionizes the world, enhancing information transfer, control, and analysis. As it expands, it will drive complex app development, problem-solving, and industry growth, according to Comp TIA.

Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning (AI & ML): AI transforms business interactions through smart websites and bots, impacting industries like retail, healthcare, finance, and education. Machine learning (ML) analyzes data to build automatic models, enabling AI to understand patterns and make decisions without assistance. These technologies provide organizations with valuable insights into their competitive landscape, execution, and resource allocation, enabling marketers to improve performance.

Automation: Robotization is rapidly growing due to advancements in cloud computing, big data, artificial intelligence, and mechanical technology, with numerous program counseling firms managing computerization arrangements across various industries.

Blockchain is a decentralized computerized record that stores global transactions, increasing security and speeding up data exchange. It involves third parties providing trust and certification. Large companies are exploring blockchain platforms for top-level trade solutions. Blockchain engineers are in high demand, working with Bitcoin and Ethereum conventions for real-world applications.

Cyber Security: Cybersecurity Think about Programs that teach how to protect computer systems and information from cyber-attacks, track devices, and reduce risks. The goal is to develop specialized skills to anticipate attacks and protect personal information. With the increasing demand for cybersecurity professionals, cybersecurity workers are rising three times faster than other tech jobs.

Voice Technology: Voice innovations like Siri and Alexa have not fully embraced human capabilities. In the future, voice commands and associates will become more valuable, blending human advances with AI, discourse recognition, and machine learning. NLP innovations will bring voice innovation to its full mechanical value.

Virtual Reality (VR) enhances user experience, and Augmented Reality (AR) enhances the environment. Major players like Google, Samsung, and Oculus dominate the VR market, but start-ups are gaining expertise. Basic programming and forward-thinking skills are required.

IOT: The Internet of Things (IoT) is transforming trade by providing necessary information for marketing, increasing deals, and reducing costs, according to a report by Comp TIA Developing Innovation Community.

Serverless Computing: Serverless computing, mechanical autonomy, quantum computing, and computerization are modern technologies that enable organizations to create mechanized, disconnected IT environments, reducing operational costs and enhancing modern capabilities.

Biometrics: Biometrics, such as face, fingerprint, and retina scans, are becoming standard methods for

confirming identity, shaping IT companies' security infrastructure in the future.

Robotics: Robotics is a significant modern invention that significantly impacts employment rates by enhancing business efficiency, speed, and cost-effectiveness.

Virtual reality (VR or Augmented reality (AR): Utilizing VR, AR, mixed reality, AI, and sensor advances can assist organizations in progressing operational effectiveness and person efficiency, according to the report.

Drones: Drones enable robotic computerization with fewer geographical restrictions, offering opportunities for advancement and integration. Intelligent apps, a blend of artificial intelligence, the internet of things, and big data analytics, will become more valuable and valuable, enabling smarter decisions like turning off lights and machines.

Computer Technology has spurred economic growth by creating employment, improving income, and improving health care and industrial processes. Computer science made the system of work easy and short. Above, the List of the latest technologies in computer science is a blessing of modern science. We can do anything within a short time by the use of this technology (Tech Republic, 2022).

In its drive to diversify the economy from oil and gas, the government is encouraging partnerships between local ICT companies and foreign investors. To promote these partnerships and grow an entrepreneurial ecosystem in the technology sector, the Nigerian government has supported government or private-sector-led incubator hubs, youth innovation programs, and science and technology parks (Tech Republic, 2022).

Much like the federal government, several states have begun implementing policies and ICT projects that may help attract ICT investments and create an enabling business climate for their regions. The Lagos state government announced the construction of a free tech zone that would allow for the growth and financing of innovative ideas and may become one of the major technology clusters in West Africa.

Similarly, the Edo state government is promoting a live-work-play project that is expected to support a dynamic environment for innovation, growth, and development in technology.

Microsoft has partnered with local accelerators like iDEA and Co-Creation Hub in Lagos, attracting foreign investors like Y Combinator and Andela. In 2022, Microsoft launched its first African Development Center in Lagos, recruiting African engineering talent for intelligent cloud and edge solutions.

The Federal Ministry of Communications and Digital Economy oversees the ICT sector, overseeing three agencies: NCC for telecoms, NBC for broadcasting, and NITDA for digital policy implementation.

The Nigerian government launched the National Digital Economy Policy and Strategy (2020-2030) in November 2019, aiming to diversify the economy and shift from dependence on the oil and gas sector. The policy focuses on 8 pillars: development regulation, digital literacy, solid infrastructure, service infrastructure, digital services, soft infrastructure, digital society, and indigenous content development. However, challenges such as long processing delays, multiple taxation, regulatory bodies, damage to infrastructure, and right-of-way charges have hindered broadband expansion and investment opportunities.

Theoretical Literatures

Adam Smith's Theory of Technological Innovation (1776)

According to Kouam and Kingsley (2023), Adam Smith conceived technology's innovative capacity as a key determinant of the economic competitiveness of nations and innovation as the engine of economic progress and welfare. According to Adam Smith, technological innovation is an instrument for solving global environmental and health challenges. He treated the growth of organizations as the result of their ability to generate new ideas in supporting increasing production, employment, and environmental protection (Kouam & Kingsley, 2023). Adam Smith (1776) not only considered technological innovation as something that brings about productivity and specialization, but also improvements brought to

the production of capital goods and the role exercised by R&D activities or technology transfer in the economy.

Technology innovation theory by R. Solow (1957)

R. Solow introduced technological innovation in 1957 in his production growth models, stating that it influences production size and determines capital and labor productivity growth. This theory is used in world industrial dynamics models to explain long-term growth variation across nations. Posner (1961) argued that the difference in economic growth between countries is due to technological innovation, while imitation decreases it. Fagerberg (1996) identified the growth gap and income reduction among states due to imitation, particularly involving technology, and identified a lack of technology innovation as a significant factor affecting economic growth rates.

Empirical Literatures

Joshua A (2023) examined the employment effects of technological innovation: evidence from Nigeria's economic sectors. Technological advancement continues to revolutionize the labor market, intensifying the debate on its employment effect across developing and developed economies. Employing the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) framework, this study provides insights into the employment-innovation nexus across the Nigerian economic sectors using the quarterly data from 2011Q1 to 2021Q4. The findings reveal that the employment-innovation nexus is a short-run phenomenon in Nigeria and that technological innovation enhances employment generation in the service sector and the agricultural sector, but it takes a quarter before the positive employment effect occurs. The results suggest that technological innovation improves employment and reallocates labor across the sectors. This suggests the need to fully operationalize technological innovation across the Nigerian economic sectors to tackle the prevailing unemployment conundrum.

Nwosu, U., & Fred (2022). The research critically examined the nexus between banking technology innovation and the sustainable growth of Nigeria during the pre- and post-COVID-19 era between 2005 and 2020, respectively. The data employed for the

study were basically obtained from CBN Statistical Bulletin 2020, in analyzing the data obtained; econometric techniques were used, such as Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL), bounce test, granger causality, unit root and major diagnostic techniques were deployed to ascertain the impact of Banking Innovation on Sustainable Growth in Pre and Post Covid Era in Nigeria. The result obtained shows a positive and significant relationship between Banking Innovation (POS, ATM, MB) and Sustainable Growth provided by the human growth Index. In light of the above result, we recommend an immense and total improvement in the usage of banking innovative products.

Jeremiah, Ubah, Bowale and Ejemeyovwi (2021) examine the effects of technological diffusion and Access to Electricity on Employment in Nigeria Demographic transitions and technological advancements may lead to a net loss of 5 million jobs by 2020; hence, about 40% (1.4 billion) of the global workforce are vulnerable to unemployment. This is because a more significant percentage of tasks that are already being disrupted by automation are repetitive and standardized processes. At the same time, actions/jobs that require empathy, genuine creativity, and critical thinking will be in high demand in the new workforce, thereby achieving human-machine collaboration. Thus, this study seeks to investigate how technology influences employment in the Nigerian labor market and how Access to electricity and employment are connected using Nigeria as a case study. The unit root test was conducted via Phillips-Perron (PP) statistics and Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) tests. The Auto-Regressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model was also employed to evaluate the relationship between technology and employment in Nigeria using World Bank data (1960-2017). Results showed that technology and globalization have a long-run statistically significant inverse relationship with employment in Nigeria, which conforms to theory. Policy recommendations promote acquiring such skills, encompassing critical thinking, empathy, and creativity, to enable a better future for the Nigerian labor force.

Oyegok and Wasiu (2021). This study examines the effects of technology innovations on unemployment in Nigeria using annual time series data from 1980 to

2018, the Autoregressive Distributed Lag and cointegration bound testing approach. The inflow of FDI proved technological innovations; the importation of machinery and equipment was an indicator of process innovation (ETC), patents represented product innovation, and total factor productivity served as the exogenous technical progress in line with Solow. The result shows that the Inward Foreign Direct Investments (INFDI) coefficient is positive (3.85), which is significant at 5%, indicating a strong positive effect of process innovation on Unemployment. Machinery & Equipment was also positive (2.87), significant at 5%. However, Patent (-1.20) negatively and significantly affects unemployment. By implication, process innovation (with Embodied Technological Change, potentially substitutes labour) raises unemployment, while product innovation reduces unemployment in Nigeria. There is a need to invest more in in-house innovation via R&D activities by upgrading the learning and skill acquisition standard of the country, and also supporting innovative ventures through discoveries, mentorship, provision of capital, and a macroeconomically stable environment

Ene (2020) examined human growth in Nigeria using the three leading indicators: education, life expectancy, and income. The researcher collected data from the yearly Nigeria HDR reports from the UNDP. Nigeria Ministry of Education, World Growth Indicators, and Nigeria Bureau of Statistics were also collected. Evident from the study shows that human growth is quite low. Nigeria is a lowly developed country. Despite abundant natural and human resources, the growth rate in Nigeria is very slow and pathetic. Education, health, and income per head in Nigeria are at a staggering low point, with several parts of Northern Nigeria living below the US\$1.50 per day poverty line, while education is at a very critical low. The result also shows that the inequality gap in Nigeria is one of the highest in Africa. Dominic, Jeremiah, Adiat, and Babatunde (2020) empirically investigate the role of innovation on human growth in West Africa (2004—2014). The estimation techniques utilized to carry out the objective were the standard variations of the generalized least squares, Panel Fixed, and Panel Random effects estimation techniques. The empirical results show that innovation in West Africa has a statistically significant positive impact on human

growth, emphasizing the potential for harnessing human growth through consistent innovation. The study recommends increased innovation through adequate research, growth funding, and university-industry partnerships to solve real human growth problems.

EEN (2019) examined the impact of technology innovation on Enterprise growth in Europe. The long-run relationship between technology innovation and enterprise growth was observed through a Vector Error Correction Model (VECM). The variables included in the VAR and VECM were card payments, mobile transactions, and electronic fund transfers as independent variables, and Real GDP as the dependent variable. Granger Causality was used to check the causality between the different variables. The study uncovered that technology innovation systems affect enterprise growth

Lionel (2018) examined the relationship among human capital, technological growth, infrastructure, and the performance of the manufacturing sub-sector in Nigeria between 1970 and 2015 through the use of the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model/ Bounds test and the Toda-Yamamoto causality test. The findings revealed, among others, that the growth of human capital, infrastructure, and technology does not lead to improvements in the performance of the manufacturing sector in Nigeria. Based on the findings, the study recommended, inter alia, that the government should formulate and implement policies aimed at improving the quantity and quality of the nation's economic infrastructure, the quantity and quality of the health services, the quantity, and the quality of the nation's human capital.

Eneji, Nnandy, Gukat, and Odey (2018) examined the effect of technology innovation on sustainable growth in Nigeria. The study used a survey method. Evaluation of findings was done using a simple percentage statistical technique. It was uncovered that technology innovation has a widespread impact on sustainable growth in Nigeria, and it is recommended that Nigeria's educational and private sectors play a leading role in technology innovation.

Global Perspective & Solutions (2018) examined the Impact of new technologies on Economic growth in Hungary. The study used multiple regression models

to analyze various variables. The results provide evidence of a positive relationship between economic growth and new technology.

Harrison, Jaumandreu, & Peters (2018) examine the impact of Innovation on employment in European Countries. The analysis was performed by using multiple regression models. In order to quantify the innovation, they used various variables, such as the number of patents, the number of trademarks, and R&D expenditures. The results provide evidence of a positive relationship between economic growth and innovation.

Danaher (2017) investigated the impact of technology innovation on the employment rate in Gambia. An ordinary least squares regression model was employed to analyze the data. The result shows a positive relationship between employment rate and technology innovation in Gambia.

Frey & Osborne (2017) examine how Susceptible jobs are to Computerization in the technology innovation era in West Africa. The study adopted the standard variations of the generalized least squares. The results show that innovation in West Africa has a statistically significant positive impact on employment. The study recommends increasing technology innovation through adequate research and growth funding.

Matuzeviciute, Mindaugas, and Karaliute (2017) examine the effect of technological Innovation on unemployment in European Countries' Economies. The autoregressive test approach was adopted. The inflow of FDI proved technological innovations; the importation of machinery and equipment was an indicator of process innovation (ETC), patents represented product innovation, and total factor productivity served as the exogenous technical progress in line with Solow. The result shows that the Inward Foreign Direct Investments (INFDI) coefficient is positive at 5%, indicating a strong positive effect of process innovation on unemployment. Machinery & Equipment was also positive (2.87), significant at 5%. However, Patent (-1.20) negatively and significantly affects unemployment. The study recommended that the country invest more in in-house innovation via R&D activities by upgrading the country's learning and skill

acquisition standard, and supporting innovative ventures through discoveries, mentorship, provision of capital, and a macroeconomically stable environment. Michael (2017) examines the effect of Robotics technology on employment in the US. The analysis was performed using multiple regression models. The results provide positive evidence between employment, robotic technology, economic growth, and innovation.

Milington, K. (2017) examined the effect of changes in technology and automat on the labour market in Africa. The analysis was performed using simple regression models estimated for The results shows a positive relationship between labour market and change in technology innovation.

Acemoglu & Restrepo (2017) investigated the effect of Robotic staff on Jobs creation in US. The ordinary least square econometric model was adopted in the analysis. It was uncovered that increase in the use of robotic staff negatively affect employment in same firms and industries in US Arntz, Gregory, & Zierahn (2016) examined the risk of automation for Jobs creation in OECD Countries. The investigator used Autoregressive Distributed Lag model. The study revealed that automation significantly affects job creation and does not lead to improvements in the performance of the manufacturing sector. the study recommended an improvement in human welfare within the job environment.

Barbieri, & Vivarelli, (2016). The standard variation of the generalized least squares Panel Fixed estimation techniques was adopted. The empirical results show that innovation in Africa has a statistically significant positive impact on economic growth. The study recommends increased innovation as solution criteria for growth in Africa

Elsevier (2015) analyze if the long term economic growth is influenced by the innovation potential of an economy. the study was performed by using multiple regression models estimated for the following CEE countries, namely Poland, Czech Republic and Hungary. In order to quantify the innovation various variables, such as number of patents, number of trademarks, R&D expenditures were used. The results provide evidence of a positive relationship between economic growth and innovation.

Andreea M, Olivera E and Florina S (2015) examine innovation and economic growth: An empirical analysis for Poland, Czech Republic and Hungary. The purpose of their paper was to analyze if the long term economic growth is influenced by the innovation potential of an economy. The analysis was performed by using multiple regression models estimated for Poland, Czech Republic and Hungary. In order to quantify the innovation they used various variables, such as number of patents, number of trademarks, R&D expenditures. The results provide evidence of a positive relationship between economic growth and innovation.

Marzena L (2015) the article presents the technology innovation in the attainment of economic progress. It reviews the economics literature and looks at the importance of innovation in different economic models. It begins with an analysis of the views of representatives of classical economics, including those of Adam Smith, David Ricardo and Jean-Baptiste Say. The study shows the growing importance of innovation, research in socio-economic growth.

Brzeski & Burk (2015) examined the impact of Automation on the German Labour Market. A regressive model and primary diagnostic techniques are used to analyze the data. The result obtained shows a negative relationship between Automation Innovation and employment in the labour market, but a positive relationship with economic growth in Germany. They recommended total improvement in the usage of automation products.

Dahlman & Chen (2014) examined the impact of technology innovation on economic Growth in South Africa. An autoregressive test was used. The result shows a significant positive impact of technology innovation on economic growth. The investigation recommended an increase in public investment in technology innovation

Bogliacino (2014) examines the impact of technological Innovation on economic growth in European nations. The multiple regression models were estimated for some selected European countries. The results provide evidence of a positive relationship between economic growth and innovation.

Ceyhun & Cakir (2014) examined technological Progress and Indicators of economic growth in the Czech Republic. A multiple regression models were adopted. In order to quantify the innovation, various variables, such as the number of patents, the number of trademarks, and R&D expenditures, were used. The results provide evidence of a positive relationship between economic growth and technological progress.

Lanier (2013) examines the effect of the technology innovation era on economic growth in Africa. Simple regression models were estimated. The results provide evidence of a positive relationship between economic growth and innovation.

Feldman (2013) examines Technological unemployment in Industrial Countries. Multiple regression models was to estimate the variables The results provide evidence of a positive relationship between economic growth and innovation.

Lipsey, S. & Sun (2010) the effect of technology innovation on employment growth in Indonesian. The unit root test was conducted via Phillips-Perron (PP) statistics and Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) tests. Results showed that technology and globalization have a long-run statistically significant inverse relationship with employment in Indonesia. The study recommendations promote the acquisition of such skills encompassing critical thinking, empathy, and creativity to enable a better future for the Indonesian labor force.

Acemoglu (2010) examined the effect of Innovation on employing in Massachusetts city. The autoregressive distribution method was applied to analyze the secondary data. The findings uncovered that innovation positively affects employment. The

investigator suggested that technological innovation should be improved across the sectors, to fully operationalize technological innovation across the Massachusetts economy.

Jalles (2010). Measure the effect of technology Innovation on Linkage in economic Growth. An autoregressive test was used to analyze the variables. The result obtained shows a positive and significant relationship between technological Innovation and economic growth.

Research Methodology

Data Sources

The data are sourced from NBS reports, UNESCO reports, and Published Journals

Estimation Techniques and Procedures.

The simple regression analysis will be used to do the ordinary least squares econometric analysis in this study in order to analyze and uncover the relationship between the topic variable. It allows us to study and summarize the relationships between variables.

Theoretical Framework

The theoretical framework is the application of theory to interpret and understand variables and data in your research study. According to Connaway and Radford (2021), cited by Chris (2023), the theoretical framework utilizes theory or theories and their constituent elements as the presumed 'working model' that drives the investigation and analysis of a social phenomenon. The theoretical framework on the effect of technology innovation on economic growth in Nigeria is conceptualized in this study based on Adam Smith (1776) and Solow's (1957) growth theory of technology innovation. This is given in Figure 3.1

Figure 3.1 Effect of Technology Innovation on Economic

Source: Author Conception (2023)

Figure 3.1 depict the effect of technology innovation on economic growth base on theoretical literature. From the figure; T1,T2,T3 and T4 represent the stage of technology, E1,E2and E3 represent innovation while D1,D2,D3.and D4 represent the level of economic growth . The figure uncover that any innovation (E) brings about a progressive change in the level of technology from T1 to T4 leading to a progressive shift in the level of economic growth from D1 to D4 respectively. The process continuous with respect to innovation from E1 to E3 and so on.

This implies that economic growth is a continuous process with respect to technology innovation. Hence technology innovation affect economic growth base on literatures.

Mathematical and Econometric Model

The mathematical model stated as $GDP = F(TE)$. Hence, the econometric model is given as $GDP = A + BTE+U$

Where GDP is the rate of economic growth
 A = is autonomous economic growth which take place without any influence of technology innovation (TE)
 B = Is marginal propensity to innovate the state of technology
 TE =Technology innovation which is the causal variable of economic growth (D)
 U = Is the disturbance variable showing the presence of other factors that also affect economic growth

In this study, the researcher measure Technology innovation in terms of innovation in information and communication technology ICTE, Banking innovation (BE) and Educational innovation (EduE)
 Therefore, the general econometric model is stated thus: $GDP= A+BX1 +BX2 +BX3 + U$. Hence, $GDP = A + BICTE +B BE +B EdE + U$

This is the summary of the theoretical framework of this investigation.

Empirical Model Specification

Given that $D = \text{Sum}(GDP, E \text{ and } HCD) = A+BTE+U$. For analytical purpose, three (3) different econometric model for ordinary Leeds square (OLS) analysis are specified in this study based on the research objections and these models include:

$$GDP = A + BICTE +U \quad (1)$$

$$GDP = A+ B BE +U \quad (2)$$

$$GDP =A+ B EduE +U \quad (3)$$

Definition of Variables and Justification for the econometric models

In the three models economic growth is represented in gross domestic product (GDP) as the dependent variable and it depend on technology innovation which is represent by ICT innovation (ICTE), banking technology innovation (BE) and education technology innovation (EduE) based on the research objective respectively

A = Is autonomous growth which take place without any influence of technology innovation

B = Is marginal propensity to innovate the state of technology which explain the extent to which technology innovation brings about change in economic growth .

U = Is the disturbance variable showing the presence of other factors that may also affect economic growth Hence the econometric models for the econometric analysis are:

$$GDP = A + BICTE +U \quad (1)$$

$$GDP = A+ B BE +U \quad (2)$$

$$GDP =A+ B EduE +U \quad (3)$$

Test of Research Hypotheses and Decision Rules

The null hypothesis (HO) will be tested at 0.05 level of significance and will be rejected if the value of the t – statistics fall outside the critical region,

Data Presentation and Analysis

Data Presentation and Analysis

Table 1.1 data on the effect of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) Innovation on Economic Growth in Nigeria

Year	ICT Innovation Rate	GDP Growth Rate
2015	9.8	2.8
2016	11.4	-1.6
2017	10.6	0.8
2018	9.9	1.9
2019	13.0	2.3
2020	13.2	-1.9
2021	6.6	3.4
2022	9.8	3.1
2023	7.9	2.5

Source: UNESCO, (2023)

Table 4.1a: Present data on ICT innovation growth rate and GDP growth rate in Nigeria from 2015- 2023

<i>Regression Statistics</i>	
Multiple R	0.756485
R Square	0.580972
Adjusted R Square	0.349682
Standard Error	1.595504
Observations	9

Table 1.1b: above depicts the values of the R, R², adjusted R² and the standard error of the estimate; the above values determine how well a regression model

fits the data. More so, the "R" column signifies multiple correlation coefficients. The value of multiple R measures the quality of the prediction of the dependent variable (GDP), in this case a value of 0.756 implies a good level of prediction. The "R Square" column depicts the R² value (coefficient of determination), which is the proportion of variance in the dependent variable that can be explained by the independent variables. The value of 0.58 implies that our independent (ICT) variables explain 58% of the variability of our dependent variable, GDP.

Table 1.1c the ANOVA table presents values that can be used to ascertain the relationship between the dependent and independent variables. The F-ratio in the ANOVA table tests whether the overall regression model is a good fit for the data. The table shows that the independent variables statistically significantly predict the dependent variable, $F(1, 7) = 5.3016$, $p > .0005$ (i.e., the regression model is a good fit of the data).

Table 1.1d coefficient table

	<i>Df</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Significance F</i>
Regression	1	13.49613	13.49613	5.301683	0.054786
Residual	7	17.81942	2.545632		
Total	8	31.31556			

Estimated model coefficients

The general form of the equation to predict Internet-Users from Population, Inflation, GDP per capita is: $GDP(Y) = -0.6033X + 7.6581$

This is extracted from the Coefficients table, as shown above. Also, the "Sig." column shows that all independent variable coefficients are statistically significantly different from 0 (zero) excluding GDP. From the regression showed that Unstandardized coefficients signify how much the GDP growth rate varies with ICT innovation rate when all other independent variables are held constant.

Probability Output

Table 1.1e: Residual and probability Output

	Coefficients	Standard		P-value	Lower	Upper	Lower	Upper
		Error	t Stat		95%	95%	95.0%	95.0%
Intercept	7.658087	2.73631	2.798691	0.026574	1.187741	14.12843	1.187741	14.12843
X								
Variable 1	-0.60328	0.262008	-2.30254	0.054786	-1.22283	0.016267	-1.22283	0.016267

Observation	Predicted		Standard
	Y	Residuals	Residuals
1	1.745904	1.054096	0.706282
2	0.78065	-2.38065	-1.59512
3	1.263277	-0.46328	-0.31041
4	1.685576	0.214424	0.143672
5	-0.1846	2.484605	1.664775
6	-0.30526	-1.59474	-1.06853
7	3.676413	-0.27641	-0.18521
8	1.745904	1.354096	0.907293
9	2.892144	-0.39214	-0.26275

Percentile	Y
5.555556	-1.9
16.66667	-1.6
27.77778	0.8
38.88889	1.9
50	2.3
61.11111	2.5
72.22222	2.8
83.33333	3.1
94.44444	3.4

Table 1.1b-1.1e Present the summary of regression output on the effect of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) Innovation on Economic Growth in Nigeria

Figure 1.1d: Summary Output of Regression Statistics Figure of the effect of ICT Technology Innovation on GDP

Figure 1.1d shows the Summary Output of Regression Statistics, Multiple R, R Square, Adjusted R Square, Standard Error, Observations, ANOVA, Regression Residual and Total.

Table 1.2a: Data on Education Technology Innovation and Economic Growth in Nigeria

Year	Education Innovation Rate	GDP Growth Rate
2015	15.1	2.8
2016	7.9	-1.6
2017	6.1	0.8
2018	7.1	1.9
2019	8.4	2.3
2020	6.5	-1.9
2021	5.4	3.4
2022	5.4	3.1
2023	8.2	2.5

Source: UNESCO, (2023)

Table 1.2: present data on education technology innovation and economic growth in Nigeria from 2015-2023.

Table 1.2b Summary Regression Statistics for Banking Technology Innovation and GDP

<i>Regression Statistics</i>	
Multiple R	0.220962
R Square	0.048824
Adjusted R Square	-0.08706
Standard Error	2.06282
Observations	9

Table 1.2c: ANOVA

	<i>df</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Significance e F</i>
Regression	1	1.528958	1.528958	0.359313	0.567775
Residual	7	29.7866	4.255228		
Total	8	31.31556			

Table 1.2b: above depicts the values of the R, R2, adjusted R2 and the standard error of the estimate; the above values determine how well a regression model fits the data. More so, the "R" column signifies multiple correlation coefficients. The value of multiple R measures the quality of the prediction of the dependent variable (GDP), in this case a value of 0.2209 implies a lower level of prediction. The "R Square" column depicts the R2 value (coefficient of determination), which is the proportion of variance in the dependent variable that can be explained by the independent variables. The value of 0.0488 implies that our independent (Education technology Innovation) variables explain 4.88% of the variability of our dependent variable, GDP.

Table 1.2c the ANOVA table presents values that can be used to ascertain the relationship between the dependent and independent variables. The F-ratio in the ANOVA table tests whether the overall regression model is a good fit for the data. The table shows that the independent variables statistically significantly predict the dependent variable, $F(1, 7) = 0.359$, $p > .0005$ (i.e., the regression model is a good fit of the data).

Table 1.2d Coefficient Table

	<i>Standard</i>				<i>Lower</i>	<i>Upper</i>
	<i>Coefficients</i>	<i>Error</i>	<i>t Stat</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>95%</i>	<i>95%</i>
Intercept	2.256093	1.469261	1.535529	0.168531	-1.21816	5.730342
X Variable 1	-0.07006	0.116871	-0.59943	0.567775	-0.34641	0.206299

Estimated model coefficients

The general form of the equation to predict GDP is: $GDP(Y) = -0.0701x + 2.2561$ this is extracted from the Coefficients table, as shown above.

Figure 1.2d: Summary of Output of the Effect of Education Technology Innovation on GDP

Figure 1.2d: shows the summary of output of Regression Statistics, Multiple RR Square, Adjusted R Square, Standard Error, Observations, ANOVA, Regression Residual and Total

Table 1.3 a: Data on the Effect of Educational Innovation in Economic Growth in Nigeria.

Year	Banking Innovation Growth Rate	GDP Growth Rate
2015	10.04	2.8
2016	10.34	-1.6
2017	26.36	0.8
2018	4.47	1.9
2019	6.24	2.3
2020	11.85	-1.9
2021	12.23	3.4
2022	8.70	3.1
2023	9.76	2.5

Source: NBS, (2023)

Table 1.3b Model Summary

Regression Statistics	
Multiple R	0.273323
R Square	0.074705
Adjusted R Square	-0.05748
Standard Error	2.034563
Observations	9

Table 1.3c: ANOVA

	Df	SS	MS	F	Significance F
Regression	1	2.339436	2.339436	0.565157	0.476701
Residual	7	28.97612	4.139446		
Total	8	31.31556			

Table 1.3 b: above depicts the values of the R, R², adjusted R² and the standard error of the estimate; the above values determine how well a regression model fits the data. More so, the "R" column signifies multiple correlation coefficients. The value of multiple R measures the quality of the prediction of the dependent variable (GDP), in this case a value of 0.273323 implies a lower level of prediction. The "R Square" column depicts the R² value (coefficient of determination), which is the proportion of variance in the dependent variable that can be explained by the independent variables. The value of 0.074705 implies that our independent (Banking Technology Innovation) variables explain 7.47% of the variability of our dependent variable, GDP.

Table 1.3c the ANOVA table presents values that can be used to ascertain the relationship between the dependent and independent variables. The F-ratio in the ANOVA table tests whether the overall regression model is a good fit for the data. The table shows that the independent variables statistically significantly predict the dependent variable, $F(1, 7) = 0.565157$, $p > .0005$ (i.e., the regression model is a good fit of the data).

Table 1.3d Coefficient Table

	Standard			Lower	
	Coefficients	Error	t Stat	P-value	95% Upper 95%
Intercept	0.704764	2.062851	0.341646	0.742644	-4.1731 5.582633
X Variable 1	0.099246	0.249261	0.39816	0.702377	0.49016 0.688654

Estimated model coefficients

The general form of the equation to predict GDP is: $GDP(Y) = 0.0992x + 0.7048$. This is extracted from the Coefficients table, as shown in table 4.3d.

Table 1.3e Residual and Probability Table for banking technology innovation and GDP

Observation	RESIDUAL OUTPUT			PROBABILITY OUTPUT	
	Predicted Y	Residuals	Standard Residuals	Percentile	Y
1	1.552737	1.247263	0.646387	5.555556	-1.9
2	1.53172	-3.13172	-1.623	16.66667	-1.6
3	0.409434	0.390566	0.202409	27.77778	0.8
4	1.942945	-0.04295	-0.02226	38.88889	1.9
5	1.818947	0.481053	0.249303	50	2.3
6	1.425937	-3.32594	-1.72365	61.11111	2.5
7	1.399316	2.000684	1.036843	72.22222	2.8
8	1.646611	1.453389	0.75321	83.33333	3.1
9	1.572352	0.927648	0.480748	94.44444	3.4

Figure 1.3a Banking Technology Innovation Line Plot

Figure 1.3d: Summary of Output of the Effect of Banking Technology Innovation on GDP

Test of Hypothesis HO2

Calculated $t = -0.07006 - 1/0.116871 = 9.15598$ Df = $9 - 2 = 7$, Level of significance @ = 0.05%, Critical t-value: 2.365

The null hypothesis which state that educational technology innovation has no significant effect on economic growth in Nigeria, is rejected at 0.05% level of significant as t-test value calculated (9.15598) is greater than the critical value (2.365) at 7 degree of freedom. Hence, educational technology innovation has a significant effect on economic growth in Nigeria.

Test of Hypothesis

Test of Hypothesis HO1:

Calculated $t = -0.60328 - 1/0.262008 = 6.1192$ Df = $9 - 2 = 7$, Level of significance @ = 0.5%, Critical t-value: 2.365

The Null Hypothesis which state that information and communication technology innovation has no significant effect on economic growth in Nigeria is rejected at 0.05% level of significant as t-test value calculated (6.1192) is greater than the critical value (2.365) at 7 degree of freedom. Hence, information and communication technology innovation has a significant effect on economic growth in Nigeria

Test of hypothesis HO3:

Calculated $t = 0.099246 - 1/0.249261 = 3.61369$ Df = $9 - 2 = 7$, Level of significance @ = 0.5% Critical t-value: 2.365

The null hypothesis, which states that banking technology innovation has no significant effect on economic growth in Nigeria, is rejected at the 0.05% level of significance as the t-test value calculated (3.61369) is greater than the critical value (2.365) at 7 degrees of freedom. Hence, banking technology innovation significantly affects economic growth in Nigeria.

Discussion of Findings

From Table 1.1, the econometrics test results show that information and communication technology innovation significantly affects economic growth in Nigeria. From the result, the independent (ICT) variables explain 58% of the variability of our dependent variable, GDP.. The ANOVA test results show that the independent variables (ICT) statistically significantly predict the dependent variable GDP, and the regression model is a good fit of the data.

From table 1.2 the result of the econometrics test shows that Educational Technology Innovation has a significant effect on economic growth in Nigeria. From the result the independent (Educational Technology Innovation) variables explain 4.88% of the variability of our dependent variable GDP. Result of the ANOVA test shows that the independent variables (Educational Technology Innovation) statistically significantly predict the dependent variable GDP and the regression model is a good fit of the data.

From table 1.3; the result of the econometrics test shows that Banking Technology Innovation has a significant effect on economic growth in Nigeria. From the result the independent (Banking Technology Innovation) variables explain 7.47% of the variability of our dependent variable GDP. Result of the ANOVA test shows that the independent variables (Banking Technology Innovation) statistically significantly predict the dependent variable GDP and the regression model is a good fit of the data.

Summary, Conclusion and Recommendation

Summaries of Findings

- From table 1.1 the result of the econometrics test shows that information and communication technology innovation has a significant effect on economic growth in Nigeria.
- It is revealed that ICT innovation explain 58% of the variability of GDP in Nigeria.
- It is revealed that ICT innovation statistically significantly predict GDP and the regression model is a good fit of the data
- From table 4.2 the result of the econometrics test shows that Educational Technology

Innovation has a significant effect on economic growth in Nigeria.

- It is revealed the Educational Technology Innovation explain 4.88% of the variability of GDP in Nigeria
- It is revealed that Educational Technology Innovation statistically significantly predicts the dependent variable GDP and the regression model is a good fit of the data.
- From table 4.3; the result of the econometrics test revealed that Banking Technology Innovation has a significant effect on economic growth in Nigeria.
- It is revealed that Banking Technology Innovation explains 7.47% of the variability of GDP in Nigeria.
- It is also revealed that Banking Technology Innovation statistically significantly predicts the dependent variable GDP and the regression model is a good fit of the data.

Conclusion

Nigeria's economic growth is significantly influenced by technology innovation, particularly in information and communication, educational, and banking sectors.

Recommendation

- Technology innovation in Nigeria should be given more attentions in all sector of the economy.
- Government budgetary allocation in education, ICT and the banking sector should be review to reflect technology innovation progressed in such areas.
- There should be a replicate of this study with reference to other sectors than ICT, Education and the banking sector in order to ascertain the specific effect of its technology innovation on economic growth in Nigeria.

References

- Acemoglu, D. & Restrepo, P. (2017). Robots. And Jobs: Evidence from US Labour Market National Bureau of Economic Research Vol 4. Page 1-91: Vol. 8, No. 1, pp. 18-23. Nigeria: IMA.
- Adenike, A. (2020). Ways technology has improved Nigerian lives since independence. Online

- Article: Retrieved on 26, August 2023 from: www.britanica.com
- Arntz, M. Gregory, T. & Zierahn, U. (2016) The Risk of Automation for Jobs in OECD Countries: A Comparative Analysis OECD. Social Employment and Migration Working Papers.
- Analyst Insight (2022). Technology innovation: Retrieved on 26 August 2023. From www.analyticiansight.net
- Andreea, M., Olivera E., & Florina S (2015). Innovation and economic growth: An empirical analysis for CEE countries. Conference on Business, Economics and Management, WCBEM Published by Elsevier B.V.
- Anne, O. (2023). Growth Focus: Council of Economic and Growth Affairs Review Vol. 26, page 43-48 Retrieved from www.britanica.com
- Azuh, D. E., Ejemeyovwi, J. O., Adiat, Q., & Ayanda, B. A. (2020). Innovation and Human Development Perspectives in West Africa. SAGE Open, 10(4), 215824402098327. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2158244020983277>
- Barbieri, L., Piva, M., & Vivarelli, M. (2016). R&D, Embodied T Micro data IZADP: Retrieved from: www.iiste.org
- Bogliacino, F. (2014) Innovation. And Employment: A Firm level Analysis with European R&DS corebodard ta Economic Elsevier. International Journal of Innovative Research and Growth Vol. 6 Issue 7: retrieved from: www.researchgate.com
- Brzeski, C. & Burk, L. (2015) The Robots. Come, Consequences of Automation for The German Labour Market ING. DiBa: Economic Research institute.
- Brett, H. (2023). Construction technology: Definition, benefits and examples: Retrieved From <https://in.indeed.com/career-advice/career-growth/construction-technology> Accessed 30th October 2023
- Career, G. (2023). Construction technology: Definition, benefits and examples: Retrieved on 25 August, From <https://www.DeviceMagic.com>
- Ceyhun, E. & Cakir, S. (2014) Technological. Progress and Scientific Indicators: A Panel Data Analysis Economics of Innovation New Technology ernational Journal of Economics, Commerce and Management United Kingdom Vol. ii, Issue 10: Retrieved from <http://ijecm.co.uk/>.
- Chris, D. (2023). Theoretical framework. Accessed August 29, from: www.helpprofessor.com.
- Danaher J (2017) Wil Life B. worth Living a World without Work? Technological Unemployment and the Meaning of Lif Springer. Journal of Public Policy and Administration Research Vol.6, No.10, Retrieved from: www.ccotiiste.org
- Darius, K. (2015). Government of Nigeria of Nigeria. Retrieved from www.Nigeria.state.gov.ng. Accessed 30th October 2023
- Dominic, E., Jeremiah, O., Adiat Q., & Babatunde, A. (2020). The Role of Research and Growth on Human Growth in West Africa (2004—2014) <https://ideas.repec.org/a/sae/sagope/v10y2020i4p2158244020983277.html> . Accessed 30th October 2023
- EEN (2019) Enterprise in Europe. New York: EEN. Retrieved from <http://www.esingapore.sg/businesssupport/technology-innovation>
- Eke, A., Agala G., & Offum, F. (2019). Growth of Innovation in Economics. Open Access Library Journal. Vol. 18, Page 132-139
- Elsevier, B. (2015). Innovation and economic growth: An Empirical Analysis for CEE Countries Economics and Finance Vol. 26 Page 461 – 467. Ghana: Academic World Research and Education Center.
- Ene, B. (2020). Human growth in Nigeria International Journal of African and Asian Studies Vol. 1.61, ISSN 2409-6938 www.iiste.org Accessed November 23, 2023.
- Eneji, M., Nnandy D., Gukat, O., & Odey, F. (2018). Technology innovation and Sustainable Entrepreneurship in Nigeria: Journal of Economics, Management and Trade Vol. 21 Page 1-16: from www.iiste.org Accessed November 23, 2023.
- Federal Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Growth (2022). The launch of the NATIP Policy booklet. Nigeria: Retrieved from <https://nssp.ifpri.info/2022/09/29/launch-of-the-national-agriculture-innovation-and->

- technology-policy-natip. Accessed 20th September 2023.
- Festus, A. (2023). Tech Innovations that have had an impact on Nigeria. The Guardian publication <https://www.devicemagic.com>
- Fieldmann, H. (2013) Technological. Unemployment in Industrial Countries Journal of Evolutionary Economics, Vol. 23, page 1099-126: Retrieved from: www.jkmofste.org
- Frey, C. b. & Osborne, M. (2017) The Future of Employment: How Susceptible are Job Computerization? Technologic Forecasting and Social Change, Journal of Economics and Business, Vol. 114, page 254–280: www.iiste.org
- Harrison P, Ruperti H, Jaumandreu T, Mairesse, J & Peters B (2018) Does Innovation Stimulate Employment? A Firm-level Analysis Comparable Micro Data on Four European Countries NBER Working. Auckland: University of Johannesburg.
- Jalles, T. (2010) How. To Measure Innovation? New Evidence of the Technology Linkage-Growth. Elsevier: Economic Research Inst.
- Joshua, A. A., (2023). Employment effects of technological innovation: evidence from Nigeria economic sectors. Economic Horizons. Volume 25, Number 1, Page 3-16
- Lanier, J. (2013). Who owns the Future? New York: Simon & Schuster publisher.
- Lipsey, R. Sjöholm, F. & Sun, J. (2010) Foreign Ownership and Employment Growth in Indonesian Manufacturing sector international Journal of Economics, Commerce and Management United Kingdom Vol. ii, Issue 10: Retrieved from <http://ijecm.co.uk/>.
- Marzena, L. (2015). Innovation in Economic Theory and the Growth of Economic Thought. [Http://acta_oeconomia.sggw.pl](http://acta_oeconomia.sggw.pl).
- Matuzeviciute, K. Mindaugas, B. & Karaliute, A. (2017) Do Technological. Innovation affect Unemployment? Some Empirical from European Countries Economies. International Journal of Economics, Commerce and Management United Kingdom Vol. ii, Issue 10: Retrieved from <http://ijecm.co.uk/>.
- Michael L. (2017). Service. Robotics and Human Labor: A First Technological Assessment Robotics and Automation System, 87348-354., Retrieved from: www.iiste.org
- Milington, K. (2017) How. Changes in technology and automatic effect on the labour market in Africa K4D Helpdesk. Report Bright to. UK: Institute of Growth Studies
- Nwani, J., Nwaimo, D., Kanu, T. & Eke G. (2020). Cashless Policy and the Nigerian Payment System International Journal of Innovation and Economic Growth Volume 5, Issue 6,
- Nwosu, E., Ubi, J., & Fred. A. (2022). Banking innovation on sustainable Growth of Nigeria during the pre and post Covid Era West African Journal of Industrial and Academic Research Vol. 23 Page 2-4. Retrieved from: <https://www.ajol.info/index.php/wajiar/issue> . Accessed October 30th, 2023
- Ozozoyin (2023). Technological innovations and unemployment in Nigeria. CBN Bullion, Vol. 45, Page 13 - 24.
- Prabha, P. (2021). Economic Growth : Definition, Scope, and Measurement Growth Retrieved from: www.researchgate.net/publication/346379002. Accessed October 25, 2023
- Smith, A. (1904). An Inquiry into the Nature and Causes of the Wealth of Nations, Methuen & Co. London. Retrieved from: <http://www.econlib.org/library/Smith/smWN1.html>. Accessed 25 October 2023
- Tech Republic (2022). Computer Technology. Retrieved From www.techrepublic.com. Accessed September 22, 2023.
- Upgrad, G. (2022). Technology Innovation. Retrieved from: www.upgrad.com. Accessed October 2, 2023
- World Bank (2023). World growth indicators. Washington, World Bank Publications Retrieved from: <http://info.worldbank.org/governance> Accessed October 22, 2023.

